

STUDIES ON CERAMIC RAW MATERIALS. PART VI. EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE AND PRESSURE ON THE BASE-EXCHANGE CAPACITY OF DIFFERENT CLAYS

BY SAROJ KUMAR CHATTERJEE

BENGAL CERAMIC INSTITUTE, GOVT. OF WEST BENGAL, CALCUTTA

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The effect of temperature alone and of varying pressures at different temperatures on the base-exchange capacities of different clays have been studied. It has been found that the clays show increased exchange capacities with increase in thermal energy up to a certain optimum temperature (60°), after which the b.e.c. values drop below the normal values. There is an initial increase in exchange capacities for the raw specimen on heat and pressure treatments, but at a pressure higher than 1.4 kg./cm², the base-exchange capacities gradually decrease and become vanishingly small due to the decomposition of the clays. The effect of pressure has been found to be more vigorous at higher temperatures, the decomposition being brought about at a much lower pressure. H-clays are more susceptible to decomposition than the raw specimen.

It appears from available literatures that very limited work has been done on the effect of temperature or pressure on cation-exchange in clays and that different views have been expressed by different investigators¹. The object of the present investigation is to study if temperatures above atmospheric simply accelerate exchange reaction or if on simultaneous application of varying pressures at different temperatures, the exchange capacity of the clays increases significantly. Obviously, in both the cases, it is expected that increased number of new ions will be able to gain access to the so-called "exchange spots". The clays, so far tested by the author, show increased exchange capacity with increase in temperature. This, however, reaches a maximum value and then again drops below the normal value. Thermal energy combined with pressure may, in general, increase the exchange initially, but the effect of increasing temperature and pressure may prove adverse to the exchange phenomenon in the long run. Specimens tested were those used in a previous communication², and the method of removal of organic matter according to Robinson³ was also the same as used therein. Analytical data of the China clay, fire-clay and Gangetic silt were recorded in Part V².

Effect of temperature on b.e.c. of clays.—The b.e.c. of the different clays at 30° was determined by the method of Parker⁴ and the data are shown in Table I.

In order to study the effect of temperature on the b.e.c. of the different clays, the ratio of the weight of the clay and the volume of normal and neutral barium acetate solution was maintained constant in each case. This is important, as significant increase in the exchange capacity is produced as the concentration of the solution is increased⁵. In each case, the equilibrium

was allowed to be established between the solid (2 g.) and the solution (50 c.c. normal) during 12 hours with occasional shaking at temperatures varying between 30° and 90°. For temperatures above 30°, the container was provided with a reflux condenser. This treatment was repeated several times. The Ba-clay was then washed free of barium acetate and leached at the ordinary temperature with neutral and normal ammonium chloride. The b.e.c. was determined by estimating the barium brought into the leaching solution. The results are shown in Table I.

TABLE I
Effect of temperature on the b.e.c. of different clays.

Substance.	B.e.c. (m.e./100 g.) at						
	30°.	40°.	50°.	60°.	70°.	80°.	90°.
Raw China clay	13.3	15.6	16.7	16.8	14.5	12.0	8.1
.. Fire-clay	18.0	21.4	23.3	23.4	19.8	16.5	10.4
.. Gangetic silt	52.2	56.9	60.0	60.2	54.5	51.1	43.1
Decarbonised China clay	10.06	12.5	13.3	13.4	11.7	9.7	5.6
.. fire-clay	14.01	17.0	18.8	18.9	15.0	12.0	6.0
.. Gangetic silt	41.6	46.1	48.9	48.98	42.9	39.1	31.1
Clean China clay	6.16	8.1	9.0	9.0	7.0	5.0	1.0
.. fire-clay	9.76	12.6	13.7	13.8	10.5	7.4	1.4
.. Gangetic silt	28.8	32.9	35.3	35.4	30.0	27.0	18.9

From Table I b.e.c. of each clay appears to increase progressively with rise in temperature and attain a maximum value at about 60°. The exchange capacities of the clays appear to decrease with further increase in temperature and this is appreciable at 90°, the values being lower than those obtained at 30°. It is likely that at the optimum temperature (near about 60°) the less accessible positions become available for exchange. According to the concept of Jenny and Reitemeier⁸, the adsorbed cations are not at rest but oscillate, and at times are at a considerable distance from the wall due to heat motion and Brownian movement. Increased temperature must cause greater frequency of oscillation of the adsorbed cations, and this would facilitate replacement by the added cations to a considerable extent. Further, the double layer thickness around a colloidal clay particle is a function of the hydration of the cations and ionic distribution⁷, and in the light of this picture, the counter-ions of the clay particles are exchanged easily with the ions from the dispersion medium.⁸ If in an aqueous solution of the electrolyte the ions are hydrated, it may be expected that the more hydrated an ion is, the more it should lose water of hydration when heated⁹. This would eventually increase the activity of the replacing cations. There is, however, no definite information about the water of hydration of the counter-ions in clays when the temperature is increased. Grim¹⁰ is of the opinion that some cations (*s.g.* Na), previously thought to be highly hydrated, probably do not hydrate at all and that other

cations hydrate to a lesser degree than what has been assumed. The hydration hull prevents close contact between the cations and the anions. Since a clay slip does not flocculate easily on heating, it may be assumed that the effect of temperature on hydrated counter-ions is not appreciable. There is thus a minimum distance between the adsorbed ions and the counter-ions of the clay particles. This, coupled with the fact that the mass action principle is also operative in this process, may explain the reason why increased exchange capacity is observed at the optimum temperature. At higher temperatures the clays are likely to suffer some amount of decomposition, and consequently the b.e.c. values decrease even below those measured at the ordinary temperature

Effect of pressure at different temperatures on b.e.c. of clays.—The effect of varying pressures at different temperatures on the b.e.c. of clays was studied in the following manner. A mixture of clay (2 g.) and 50 c.c. of neutral and normal barium acetate solution kept in a container was placed inside a chamber fitted with a thermometer and an arrangement for regulating pressure by means of compressed air. Heat was applied externally, and a particular temperature and pressure were maintained for 12 hours in every case. This treatment with barium acetate was repeated several times. The clay was then washed free of barium acetate and leached at the ordinary temperature with neutral and normal ammonium chloride solution. The b.e.c. in each case was determined by estimating the barium in the leachate. The results obtained with raw specimens have been incorporated in Table II and those obtained with decarbonised and electro-dialysed specimens in Table III.

TABLE II

Substance.	Temp.	B.e.c. (m.e./100 g.) at pressure of kilos/cm ² .								
		1.40.	1.60.	1.80.	2.0.	2.2.	2.4.	2.6.	2.8.	3.0.
China clay	70°	18.8	10.2	6.1	4.2	2.1	0.97	Nil	Nil	Nil
Fire-clay	"	24.4	16.6	10.1	5.2	1.2	0.50	"	"	"
Gangetic silt	"	59.9	51.0	42.3	32.1	26.2	14.2	6.2	"	"
China clay	80°	14.0	7.1	4.0	1.4	Nil	Nil	Nil	"	"
Fire-clay	"	18.0	8.3	4.9	1.9	"	"	"	"	"
Gangetic silt	"	54.2	42.2	29.2	18.6	8.2	"	"	"	"
China clay	90°	8.8	2.9	0.2	Nil	Nil	"	"	"	"
Fire-clay	"	11.0	4.2	0.6	"	"	"	"	"	"
Gangetic silt	"	44.2	32.0	21.3	10.1	2.2	"	"	"	"

Comparing the data incorporated in Table III with those shown for 70°-90° in Table II for those materials, it will be observed that there is an initial increase of b.e.c. corresponding to 1.4 kg./cm². At higher pressures, the b.e.c. gradually decreases and becomes vanishingly small, when it is likely that the clays are completely decomposed. A physical examination of the materials

after pressure treatment shows somewhat jelly-like masses. The effect of pressure, as will be evident from Table III, is more vigorous at higher temperatures, the decomposition being brought about at a much lower pressure.

TABLE III

Substance.	Temp.	B.e.c. (m. e./100 g.) at a pressure of kilos/cm ² .								
		1.4	1.6	1.8	2.0	2.2	2.4	2.6	2.8	3.0
H-China clay	70°	11.4	8.1	5.6	1.2	0.5	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
H-Fire-clay	"	15.0	11.2	7.2	3.1	1.8	"	"	"	"
H-Silt	"	38.0	31.2	22.7	12.3	7.1	2.2	"	"	"
H-China clay	80°	4.7	3.2	2.0	0.4	Nil	Nil	"	"	"
H-Fire-clay	"	6.2	5.1	2.4	0.9	"	"	"	"	"
H-Silt	"	25.1	20.2	11.2	5.0	1.1	"	"	"	"
H-China clay	90°	0.89	0.3	Nil	Nil	Nil	"	"	"	"
H-Fire-clay	"	1.0	0.6	"	"	"	"	"	"	"
H-Silt	"	15.5	12.1	9.9	2.1	"	"	"	"	"

A difference between the raw and the H-clay towards heat and pressure treatments is also to be mentioned. Whereas the raw clay shows an increase in b.e.c. at 1.40 kg./cm². at all the temperatures studied, the H-clay shows the increase only at 70°. This indicates that the H-clay is more susceptible to decomposition than the raw one.

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